

Multivariate analysis based evaluation of maize genotypes under high temperature stress

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Abstract

The pace of world population growth is very rapid, and the main culprit in this phenomenon is urbanization. The demand for food is also expected to increase, especially for crops used as staple foods. To counter these problems, collaboration is needed among different organizations in the world. In response to this situation the Maize and Millets Research Institute, Yusafwala, Sahiwal, Pakistan (MMRI) is working with the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT) on different projects to identify and characterize heat-tolerant genotypes. High temperatures affect pollination and seed setting rates, and have reduced maize yields significantly by as much as 80% to 90%. A trial named HSH-II-117 with 70 maize accessions (64 imported from CIMMYT, Mexico and 6 local checks) was carried out at MMRI in spring 2017 under a randomized complete block design with two replications. Data were collected for different morphological traits. Statistically significance differences among genotypes were determined, and principle components analysis and cluster analysis were used. Significant differences among genotypes were found for all traits except ear height. The percentage coefficient of variance (CV%) for all traits was less than 20%, so all traits could be used for further analysis. Genotypes P1543©, ZH1635, FH949©, ZH1639 and ZH16902 can be recommended as short-duration, high-yield genotypes, while YH1898©, ZH16900 and ZH1655 can be recommended as medium-duration, high-yield genotypes. All the recommended genotypes had the lowest stem lodging and root lodging, and the shortest time to the end of anthesis.

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Introduction

The world population is expected to grow by more than 90% between 2009 and 2050 compared to the previous four decades. The largest share of this growth is forecast for developing countries. Urbanization continues at an accelerating pace and is predicted to account for 70% of the world population in 2050, and the rural population, after peaking sometime in the next decade, is expected to actually decline. These figures show that the demand for food will continue to grow. In particular, the demand for cereals as both food and feed is projected to reach some 3 billion tonnes by 2050, and was recently estimated at nearly 2.1 billion tonnes (FAOSTAT, 2017). The projections show that in order to feed the entire world population, food production will need to almost double. However, some countries will be unable to increase their food production to meet this goal.

To counteract these problems, collaboration among different organizations is needed. Because agriculturalists are the principal managers of global food markets, collaboration between international agricultural organizations is urgently needed. In response to this situation, the Maize and Millets Research Institute (MMRI), Yusufwala, Sahiwal, Pakistan is working with the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT) on different projects such as the Agriculture Innovation Program (AIP) and the evaluation of maize genotypes under heat stress (Heat Tolerant Maize for Asia (HTMA)).

Heat stress is one of the major threats to agricultural production. The reproductive stage is the most sensitive stage to high temperatures. High temperatures affect pollination and seed setting, and can significantly reduce maize yields by as much as 80% to 90% (Hatfield et al., 1976; Yousaf et al., 2017; Yousaf et al., 2018).

Maize (also known as corn) is the third most important crop of Pakistan as well as worldwide (see PARC, <http://www.parc.gov.pk>). This crop is well known due to the versatility of its food and non-food products such as biofuel and fodder from stalks, and livestock feed from grains (Sapkota & Pokhrel, 2010; Tariq & Iqbal, 2010). In Pakistan, maize is an attractive crop because it produces two harvests per year (*kharif* [beginning in autumn] and spring) (Tariq & Iqbal, 2010). This crop accounts for 2.2% of the added value in agriculture, and for 0.4% of the gross domestic product of Pakistan. Maize is currently cultivated on a total area of 13.34 million hectares, which is 12% larger than in the previous year, with a production of 61.3 million tonnes (Govt. of Pakistan, 2017-2018).

Genetic diversity, an important factor in efforts to improve maize genotypes, can be assessed through different methods (Govindraj et al., 2015). Principle components analysis (PCA) can be used to reduce the number of variables, facilitate their interpretation, and identify correlations between genotypes and traits. Cluster analysis is a multivariate method that can be used to classify a sample of objects on the basis of a set of measured variables into a number of different groups according to their similarities. Hence similarities among genotypes can be estimated with the help of cluster analysis (Evgenidis et al., 2011). In the present study the genetic diversity of maize genotypes was assessed in genotypes provided by CIMMYT (cultivated under the HTMA project) and in local checks through cluster analysis and PCA. The findings will be helpful in further efforts to evaluate the suitability of these genotypes for cultivation under heat stress conditions in the Pakistani environment.

Materials and Methods

A trial named HSH-II-117 consisted of 70 maize accessions (64 imported from CIMMYT, Mexico and 6 local checks) that were planted at MMRI,

Pakistan in Spring 2017 under a randomized complete block design with two replications. Plot size was 5 × 3 m. All agronomic practices, i.e., irrigation, fertilizer application, pesticide application, hoeing and thinning, etc. were performed at the appropriate times. Five plants were selected randomly from each entry for data collection.

Data were collected for the following traits: days to flowering in males, days to flowering in females, days to end of anthesis, plant height, ear height, root lodging, stem lodging, number of ears, number of plants, field weight of cobs, grain moisture, grain weight and ear aspect. For root lodging and stem lodging, the number of plants affected was calculated, while for ear aspect, a scale of 1 to 5 was used. Genotypes with very good characteristics were scored as 1, and those with very poor characteristics were scored as 5.

Statistical significance of the differences was computed according to Steel et al. (1997) with the help of Statistix 8.1. Principle component analysis and cluster analysis were done according to Sneath and Sokal (1973) with the help of XLSTAT.

Results and Discussion

Significant differences among genotypes were found for all traits except ear height (nonsignificant differences). The percentage coefficient of variance (CV%) for all traits was less than 20%, so all traits could be used for further analysis (Table 1). Sharma et al. (2014) observed significant differences among 20 maize genotypes for days to 50% flowering, cob length, plant height, 100 grain weight, grain yield per plant and stalk weight.

Table 1. Analysis of variance.

Source	DF	Ear height	Days to end of anthesis	Field weight	Grain moisture	Female flowering	Male flowering	No. of ears	No. of plants	Plant height	Grain yield
Rep	8	21.6 ^{NS}	96.11 ^{NS}	2.96 ^{NS}	2.56 ^{NS}	46.87 ^{NS}	46.86 ^{NS}	45.71 ^{NS}	36.01 ^{NS}	9.779 ^{NS}	1.87 ^{NS}
Gen	69	24648.0 ^{NS}	378.17 ^{**}	1.27 ^{**}	0.64 ^{**}	5.36 ^{**}	5.41 ^{**}	61.86 ^{**}	61.62 ^{**}	665.66 [*]	0.77 ^{**}
Error	69	24790.9	262.87	0.77	0.68	2.82	2.79	21.58	21.22	397.03	0.67
Total	139										
CV		16.58	2.97	18.67	4.70	2.75	2.83	17.61	17.89	9.66	18.45

Principle components analysis

In this study total variation was divided into 11 principal components (PCs). Four PCs had eigenvalues greater than 1 and explained 73.38% of the total variance in the results. Eigenvalues are important in numerical diagnostics to evaluate how variations among large numbers of variables influence their dependence structure, and to build data matrices to

Table 2. Principle components analysis.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
Eigenvalue	3.106	2.408	2.045	1.063	0.949	0.702	0.412	0.206	0.107	0.001	0.000
Variability (%)	28.237	21.889	18.594	9.659	8.631	6.380	3.749	1.874	0.976	0.009	0.001
Cumulative %	28.237	50.126	68.720	78.380	87.011	93.391	97.140	99.014	99.990	99.999	100.000

facilitate graphical displays (Greenacre, 2010). The variance explained by the remaining PCs was lower, and the influence of factors 9 to 11 was negligible (Table 2). Total variance was also illustrated in a scree plot (Figure 1), which indicated that the first four PCs explained most of the variance, with successively smaller proportions of variance explained by the remaining PCs.

Figure 1. Scree plot of eigenvalues versus cumulative variance explained in maize genotypes tested in this study

The largest PC correlated strongly with female days to 50% flowering (0.928), with considerable positive factor loading, and showed a strong negative correlation with grain weight (-0.457), with negative factor loading. The second PC had a strong correlation with ear height (0.737), with considerable positive factor loading, while grain moisture (-0.061) yielded considerable negative factor loading. Principal component 3 correlated strongly with grain weight (0.777), with positive factor loading, and with root lodging (-0.443), which showed negative factor loading. Principal component 4 reflected positive factor loading for ear aspect (0.741) and negative factor loading for grain moisture (-0.519) (Table 3).

Genotypes ZH1644R (5.963), ZH16918 (4.928) and ZH16931 (3.709) contributed the most to total variation in PC1. ZH16840 (4.294), ZH16843 (3.743) and ZH16911 (2.721) made the largest contributions to

PC2. ZH16878 (2.811), YH1898© (2.608) and ZH161027 (2.599) made the largest contributions to PC3. HC2040© (2.405), ZH16953 (2.165) and ZH16848 (2.016) made the largest contributions to PC4 (Table 4).

Table 3. Factor loading.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
Male 50% flowering days	0.922	0.149	0.320	0.033	0.053	-0.054	0.002	0.026	-0.131	-0.022	0.000
Female 50% flowering days	0.928	0.141	0.309	0.040	0.048	-0.050	0.007	0.033	-0.127	0.022	0.000
End of anthesis	0.915	0.137	0.218	-0.037	0.117	-0.062	-0.085	-0.017	0.266	0.000	0.000
Plant height	-0.105	0.733	0.047	-0.278	-0.383	0.247	-0.375	0.154	-0.008	0.000	0.000
Ear height	0.134	0.737	-0.061	-0.297	-0.390	0.088	0.405	-0.153	0.017	0.000	0.000
Root lodging	-0.452	0.333	0.772	0.076	0.260	0.114	0.048	-0.008	0.007	-0.001	-0.009
Stem lodging	0.193	-0.061	-0.379	-0.519	0.575	0.462	0.018	-0.025	-0.024	0.000	0.000
Field weight	-0.457	0.332	0.777	0.093	0.237	0.097	0.046	-0.008	0.012	0.001	0.009
Grain moisture	0.240	0.158	-0.308	0.741	-0.059	0.511	0.085	0.048	0.021	0.000	0.000
Grain weight	-0.128	0.690	-0.443	0.051	0.327	-0.304	0.175	0.279	0.016	0.000	0.000
Ear aspect	-0.068	0.735	-0.400	0.241	0.258	-0.184	-0.241	-0.276	-0.037	0.000	0.000

From the above results it can be inferred that PC1 represents the positive influence of female days to flowering, so selection based on genotypes ZH1644R, ZH16918 and ZH16931 would result in the creation of long-duration varieties, also their grain weight would probably be low as suggested by the negative factor loading of grain weight. Selection based on these genotypes would thus not be expected to be favorable. The second PC is explained by positive ear height; thus selection based on ZH16840, ZH16843 and ZH16911 would not be expected to be favorable because it would result in low yields. Principal component 3 is explained by the positive factor loading for grain weight and negative factor loading for grain moisture and root lodging, so selection based on genotypes ZH16878, YH1898© and ZH161027 would be expected to favor efforts to obtain varieties with high grain yields and less lodging. Principal component 4 represents the positive influence of ear aspect and the negative influence of grain moisture; selection based on HC2040©, ZH16953 and ZH16848 would thus be desirable because it would favor good ear aspect and lower grain moisture.

Suryanarayana et al. (2017) applied PCA and cluster analysis to data for 30 maize accessions in India. In their study the first five PCs had eigenvalues greater than 1, which collectively explaining 85.31% of the variance. They identified days to 50% anthesis, ear length and number of kernels per row as the factors that made the greatest contributions to total variance. Pahadi et al. (2017) found eigenvalues greater than 1 for their first two PCs, which explained 73.7% of the variance. They noted that days to 50% anthesis was the most influential trait. Ali et al. (2015) found eigenvalues greater than 1 for their first three PCs, which accounted for 89.60% of the variance in maize hybrids grown in Pakistan.

Table 4. Contribution of genotypes in vector

Observation	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
DK-6724©	-2.093	-1.567	1.244	0.703	0.749	0.450	0.049	0.325	0.511	-0.008	-0.005
FH-949©	1.927	-0.656	2.054	0.914	-0.288	-0.701	0.430	0.280	0.158	-0.001	0.009
HC-2040©	-1.812	-1.817	-0.169	2.405	0.075	0.775	-0.513	0.535	0.075	-0.024	0.005
NC-8711©	-1.971	-3.008	0.075	-0.940	1.704	-0.289	-0.539	0.286	-0.242	0.003	-0.005
P-1543©	0.158	-2.534	-1.466	-1.252	0.480	0.308	-0.978	0.682	-0.525	-0.010	0.007
YH-1898©	-0.916	1.420	2.608	1.741	0.666	-0.922	0.338	-0.589	0.123	0.024	0.021
ZH137413	1.943	0.765	-4.194	-1.467	0.841	0.133	-0.005	-0.859	-0.498	0.001	0.016
ZH141592	-1.075	-0.324	1.748	0.017	0.663	-0.141	-0.154	-0.276	-0.501	0.021	0.004
ZH15266	-1.438	-2.204	-1.248	-0.327	-0.588	-0.710	0.376	-0.398	0.358	-0.015	-0.007
ZH15445	-1.203	1.175	-0.489	-0.397	-0.371	-0.908	-0.231	0.371	-0.081	0.003	0.002
ZH161003	-2.292	1.277	-1.986	0.005	2.017	-1.562	0.322	0.149	0.233	0.000	-0.006
ZH161005	-1.222	-0.468	-0.760	0.221	-0.539	0.127	-0.817	-0.442	0.509	-0.005	-0.008
ZH161027	0.886	0.002	2.599	-1.209	0.183	-0.572	0.286	-0.016	0.461	0.018	0.001
ZH1617	3.678	-0.343	0.750	0.878	-0.606	-0.107	-0.121	0.366	0.270	-0.010	0.003
ZH1619	1.628	0.078	1.810	0.295	-0.164	-0.061	0.450	-0.071	0.315	0.005	0.002
ZH1623	0.049	1.714	-2.621	-1.202	0.530	0.477	-0.752	0.324	0.338	-0.006	0.007
ZH1623R	1.894	1.074	1.042	1.347	0.679	-0.225	-0.006	0.535	-0.630	0.006	-0.011
ZH1624	-1.564	-1.001	0.905	-0.260	-0.615	-0.146	-0.193	0.460	-0.425	0.001	0.003
ZH163	-0.749	-0.758	0.009	-1.435	-0.220	0.603	0.791	-0.217	-0.046	0.000	-0.006
ZH1630	-1.446	-1.707	0.406	0.273	-0.922	-1.010	0.470	0.013	0.083	-0.009	0.002
ZH1635	0.324	-2.791	-3.404	0.817	-0.348	1.052	0.279	0.022	0.216	-0.156	-0.003
ZH1639	0.559	-1.074	-0.143	-0.366	-0.335	0.375	0.820	-0.103	0.241	-0.011	-0.003
ZH1640	-1.393	-1.520	-1.484	0.917	-1.136	0.296	1.001	-0.431	-0.379	-0.020	0.001
ZH1644	-1.391	-3.076	-1.350	0.614	-0.014	-0.395	1.310	-0.368	-0.425	-0.019	0.018
ZH1644R	5.963	-1.846	-0.076	0.080	1.258	-2.083	-0.098	-0.798	-0.072	0.010	-0.004
ZH1645	-0.602	-2.232	-0.425	-0.547	0.264	-0.225	-0.004	0.181	-0.117	-0.008	0.001
ZH1650	-0.193	-1.192	-0.702	0.948	-1.825	0.071	0.359	0.336	0.364	-0.029	-0.003
ZH1652	-1.721	-1.677	-0.025	0.633	-0.751	-0.188	0.817	-0.052	0.120	-0.014	0.027
ZH1652R	-1.394	-0.378	-0.674	0.426	1.292	-0.074	0.767	-0.908	-0.122	0.005	-0.041
ZH1655	-1.243	1.562	0.028	0.298	-0.139	-1.764	0.347	0.775	-0.163	0.000	-0.013
ZH1655R	0.415	0.426	2.014	-1.107	0.543	0.646	0.066	-0.040	0.180	0.018	0.022
ZH1672	-2.242	-0.675	-0.654	-0.223	1.552	-0.455	0.073	-0.139	0.270	0.001	-0.005
ZH1673	-1.576	-1.692	0.801	-0.916	1.752	0.891	0.066	0.122	0.091	0.004	-0.007
ZH1673R	-0.832	-2.117	1.061	0.022	1.188	-0.221	-0.326	0.412	-0.079	0.001	-0.008
ZH16817	-0.786	-0.441	0.414	-1.964	-0.082	0.152	-0.474	-0.009	0.258	0.009	-0.007
ZH16834	-0.979	-0.213	-0.752	0.105	-0.905	0.329	-2.222	0.383	0.202	-0.005	-0.001
ZH16840	0.305	4.294	-0.817	-0.183	2.653	-0.764	0.782	0.854	0.119	0.009	-0.006
ZH16843	0.033	3.743	0.660	-0.374	-1.315	-0.283	1.384	0.048	0.424	0.005	0.005
ZH16848	2.504	-0.164	-1.685	2.016	-0.571	0.604	1.401	-0.800	0.083	-0.023	0.000
ZH16849	3.376	-1.296	-0.451	-0.455	-0.376	-0.083	-0.372	0.516	0.331	-0.015	0.006
ZH16869	0.433	0.761	-0.511	-0.473	-1.647	1.559	-0.337	0.326	-0.015	-0.011	0.002
ZH16878	-0.758	2.101	2.811	0.259	0.902	2.203	-0.017	-0.328	0.050	0.025	-0.012
ZH16897	-1.790	2.255	-0.386	-1.027	-0.726	-0.207	-0.104	0.174	-0.077	0.009	0.002
ZH16899	-2.641	2.597	-0.492	1.352	-1.410	0.075	-0.884	-0.183	-0.469	0.008	0.002
ZH16900	-0.671	1.284	-0.807	-2.191	-0.009	-0.313	-0.331	-0.166	0.179	0.013	-0.006
ZH16902	0.173	-0.679	1.052	0.648	-0.482	-0.231	-0.528	0.370	0.706	-0.008	-0.003
ZH16903	-1.767	-1.055	0.944	-0.148	-0.634	-0.255	-0.151	0.376	0.040	-0.002	0.004
ZH16910	0.239	2.476	-2.579	0.372	-1.099	-0.297	-0.367	-0.026	0.076	-0.010	0.000
ZH16911	-2.114	2.721	-2.066	0.725	0.431	-1.571	0.590	0.474	-0.033	-0.006	0.003
ZH16914	0.624	-0.016	-0.172	-1.200	-1.662	-0.206	-0.039	-0.058	0.395	-0.005	-0.012
ZH16918	4.928	0.588	-2.581	0.481	1.020	0.244	-0.066	0.935	-0.196	-0.022	0.021
ZH16928	-0.174	0.970	0.435	-0.098	-0.979	0.298	-0.154	0.095	-0.677	0.008	0.002
ZH16929	-0.788	0.849	1.203	-1.049	-1.914	-0.967	-0.206	-0.340	-0.462	0.021	0.035
ZH16929R	1.869	-0.230	-1.247	0.395	-1.057	-0.871	-1.272	-0.587	0.190	-0.002	-0.021
ZH16930	0.304	-0.080	2.030	-1.269	-0.391	-0.553	0.102	0.136	0.002	0.015	-0.002
ZH16931	3.709	-0.798	0.457	0.658	-0.516	0.084	-0.001	0.597	0.043	-0.015	-0.013
ZH16934	-0.628	0.598	-1.182	-0.074	0.307	1.229	0.202	-0.235	0.567	-0.009	0.020
ZH16934R	1.457	0.867	0.943	1.839	0.101	0.863	-0.608	-0.309	-0.240	0.007	-0.013
ZH16942	-0.160	0.453	0.944	-0.807	0.931	0.355	-0.452	-0.824	-0.119	-0.173	0.000
ZH16946	-0.215	0.550	0.244	0.893	0.315	0.429	0.394	0.702	-0.587	-0.005	0.004
ZH16949	2.190	0.591	0.325	-0.763	0.024	1.939	0.448	0.121	-0.712	0.003	-0.012
ZH16952	2.121	-1.143	1.228	-0.274	0.066	-0.829	0.367	0.123	-0.228	0.004	-0.013
ZH16953	-1.946	0.601	-0.735	2.165	0.978	1.838	0.230	0.355	0.070	-0.018	-0.006
ZH16955	0.800	1.254	0.960	-0.606	-0.142	2.116	0.460	-0.085	0.025	0.005	-0.007
ZH16963	0.906	2.559	-0.896	0.477	0.308	0.306	-0.574	-0.883	0.446	0.011	-0.004
ZH16972	0.862	-0.402	-0.212	-3.002	0.057	0.666	0.548	-0.264	-0.212	0.010	0.002
ZH16974	-1.274	0.580	1.741	-0.732	-0.744	0.291	0.546	-0.213	-0.139	0.014	0.004
ZH1770	0.989	0.717	1.845	0.089	-1.370	-1.032	-0.333	-0.085	-0.407	0.016	-0.031
ZH1770R	1.288	0.089	2.021	0.883	2.275	0.088	-1.168	-0.580	0.219	0.029	0.038
ZH1771	-1.474	0.182	0.031	1.429	0.088	-0.651	-1.468	-1.077	-0.465	0.022	0.002

Figure 2. Biplot of larger PCs in maize genotypes tested in this study.

Biplot of maize genotypes

Biplot analysis clearly illustrated a strong correlation between days to male flowering, days to female flowering and days to end of anthesis. It also showed the close association between plant height, stem lodging and root lodging. A close association was also observed between field weight and grain weight.

Negative correlations can also be estimated from the biplot: traits located opposite each other were negatively correlated. Thus field weight and grain weight were negatively correlated with grain moisture (Figure 2). Correlations between genotypes and traits can also be explained by

their orientations with respect to different axes (Figure 2), as detailed below.

- 1) ZH16897, ZH16899 and ZH16911 were positively correlated with plant height, male root lodging and stem lodging, whereas P1543©, ZH1635, FH949©, ZH1639 and ZH16902 were negatively correlated with plant height, male root lodging and stem lodging.
- 2) YH1898©, ZH16900, ZH1655 and ZH16878 were positively correlated with field weight and grain weight, whereas ZH16930, ZH16972, ZH16902 and ZH16914 were negatively correlated with field weight and grain weight, and positively correlated with grain moisture.
- 3) ZH16918 was positively correlated with male days to 50% flowering, female days to 50% flowering and days to end of anthesis. DK6724©, HC2040©, ZH16903, ZH1652 and NC8711© were negatively correlated with male days to 50% flowering, female days to 50% flowering and days to end of anthesis.
- 4) ZH16840 and ZH16843 were positively correlated with ear height, whereas ZH1644 and NC8711© were negatively correlated with ear height.

Aslam et. al. (2014) analyzed 34 maize genotypes by using a biplot. This allowed them to estimate correlations among different traits and predict different selection indicators.

Table 5. Cluster analysis (Class centroids).

Class	Male 50% flowering days	Female 50% flowering days	End of anthesis	Plant height	Ear height	Field weight	Grain moisture	Grain weight	Ear aspect	Root lodging	Stem lodging
1	59.000	61.012	65.488	202.902	111.951	4.738	17.538	3.678	2.329	0.488	7.927
2	58.685	60.667	65.537	214.167	117.870	4.739	17.604	3.676	2.574	16.667	57.778
3	62.500	64.500	69.250	167.500	115.000	3.425	17.600	2.652	3.000	2.500	37.500

Table 6. Genotypes in cluster analysis.

Cluster no.	No. of genotypes	Genotype name	Significant traits
1	41	DK-6724©, FH-949©, HC-2040©, NC-8711©, P-1543©, YH-1898©, ZH141592, ZH15266, ZH161027, ZH1617, ZH1619, ZH1624, ZH163, ZH1630, ZH1635, ZH1639, ZH1640, ZH1644, ZH1645, ZH1650, ZH1652, ZH1655R, ZH1673, ZH1673R, ZH16817, ZH16849, ZH16869, ZH16878, ZH16902, ZH16903, ZH16914, ZH16928, ZH16929, ZH16930, ZH16931, ZH16946, ZH16949, ZH16952, ZH16955, ZH16972, ZH1770	Highest traits (means) Grain weight, Field weight Average traits (means) Male days to 50% flowering, Female days to 50% flowering, Plant height Lowest traits (means) Root lodging, Stem lodging, End of anthesis, Ear height, Grain moisture, Ear aspect
2	27	ZH137413, ZH15445, ZH161003, ZH161005, ZH1623, ZH1623R, ZH1652R, ZH1655, ZH1672, ZH16834, ZH16840, ZH16843, ZH16897, ZH16899, ZH16900, ZH16910, ZH16911, ZH16918, ZH16929R, ZH16934, ZH16934R, ZH16942, ZH16953, ZH16963, ZH1770R, ZH16974, ZH1771	Highest traits (means) Plant height, Ear height, Root lodging, Stem lodging, Grain moisture Average traits (means) End of anthesis, Field weight, Grain weight, Ear aspect Lowest traits (means) Male days to 50% flowering, Female days to 50% flowering
3	2	ZH1644R, ZH16848	Highest traits (means) Male days to 50% flowering, Female days to 50% flowering, End of anthesis, Ear aspect Average traits (means) Ear height, Root lodging, Stem lodging, Grain moisture Lowest traits (means) Plant height, Field weight, Grain weight

Figure 3. Cluster analysis of similarity among maize genotypes tested in this study.

Cluster analysis

The 70 genotypes we compared were grouped into three clusters (Table 5). The first cluster comprised 41 genotypes, cluster 2 consisted of 27 genotypes, and cluster 3 consisted of 2 genotypes (Table 6). These results were further confirmed by the tree diagram, which showed three distinct groups (Figure 3). The first group was the best group in terms of performance in terms of grain weight and field weight.

On comparing our PCA results (genotype contributions and biplot) with the results of cluster analysis, YH1898©, ZH16900, ZH1655 and ZH16878 were found to be best for field weight and grain weight. ZH16918 was best for the selection of long-duration, short-height plants with less root lodging and less stem lodging. DK6724©, P1543©, ZH1635, FH949©, ZH1639 and ZH16902 were the best for low root lodging and stem lodging. ZH1644R, ZH16848 were the best for the selection of plants with medium ear height, but these genotypes had the longest period (days) to 50% flowering in both male and female plants.

Suryanarayana et al. (2017) investigated 30 maize genotypes with cluster analysis and observed six clusters. They also compared the results of PCA and cluster analysis, and identified five useful genotypes for future breeding programs. Pahadi et al. (2017) categorized maize genotypes in two clusters with the help of cluster analysis. They observed that cluster 2 was the most informative, and predicted that the selection of genotypes in cluster 2 would be the most useful for future breeding programs. Ali et al. (2015) divided genotypes into three clusters with the help of cluster analysis, and observed the best-performing genotypes in cluster 3 with respect to grain yield. Tanavar et al. (2014) separated 13 maize genotypes into four clusters, and found that the most important cluster was cluster 2 for grain yield and related traits, and also contained the largest number of genotypes. They predicted that crosses between genotypes in the two high-performing clusters 2 and 4 would result in high heterosis. Similar findings were observed by Ali et al. (2008), who identified high-yielding genotypes with the help of cluster analysis. Singh and Dwivedi (2005) estimated genetic divergence among maize genotypes with the aim of identifying the best-performing genotypes.

Conclusion

Significant differences among genotypes were found for all traits except ear height. The CV% of all traits was less than 20%, so all traits could be used for further analysis. Genotypes P1543©, ZH1635, FH949©, ZH1639 and ZH16902 are likely to be useful as short-duration, high-yielding genotypes, while YH1898©, ZH16900 and ZH1655 can be recommended as medium-duration, high-yielding genotypes. All genotypes

recommended here on the basis of our results had the lowest stem lodging and root lodging, and the shortest time to the end of anthesis.

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